

Frequently Asked Questions: Promotion & Tenure for Community-Based Researchers

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Q: How do I include community-based work in a way that counts?

A: Community-based research contributions often differ from traditional academic outputs. To ensure they are recognized, document your roles clearly using formal titles like “Community Liaison,” “Knowledge Co-Producer,” or “Policy Co-Developer” in your dossier narrative, and parts of your CV such as partnerships, service, and committees. Detail the scope and scale of these contributions using timeframes, number and type of participants, and outcomes. Attach Community MOUs, co-authored documents, or media coverage where possible. Highlight relational and process-based contributions in your narrative sections, using language that aligns with your institution’s P&T criteria. If your unit doesn’t have specific language, use terms drawn from comparable recognized practices, like those used for key funders or professional organizations in your discipline.

Q: How can I make relationship-building and trust work legible in my CV or file?

A: This kind of work is fundamental to community-based research but often invisible in traditional CV formats. Assigning it a title (e.g., 'Workshop Organizer,' 'Community Network Steward') and including the timespan makes it legible. You might also include metrics like number of community meetings facilitated or attended, numbers of attendees at large events, long-term partnerships maintained, invitations issued, protocols co-developed, and number of hours per week or month spent in community. These roles should appear alongside your publications and grants in the research section of your CV and dossier, not buried under 'service.'

When you include the number of years of a partnership or project in your CV or narrative, be sure to include the number of years “Scoping” or building up relationships in the timeframe.

Q: How do I handle work that doesn’t result in a public product, like reports used only within a community?

A: Just like classified industry or government research, non-public outputs are valid and meaningful scholarly products. You can list them in the non-peer-reviewed publication portion of

your CV with a note like 'Internal Report, not publicly available.' Describe their use and impact in the narrative: e.g., 'Cited in community planning documents and used for food security advocacy.' These outputs should be in your publications section under a heading such as “white papers,” “research reports,” and/or “technical reports” depending on the type of work you do.

Q: What if my publication count is low, but my research had a large impact?

A: Promotion and tenure committees are increasingly open to diverse definitions of impact, so long as you define and provide evidence for your impact. Explain the reach and effect of your work: uptake by communities, change in policy, use in curriculum, or shifts in discourse. Where possible, include testimonies, citations in non-academic texts or policy (not just how many, but what they said about your work), diversity of citations (e.g. you studied frogs but your research is cited in studies of salmon, belugas, and bears), which countries your work is cited (use [SAGE policy profiles](#)), collaborative governance outcomes, applications of your findings or funding that are still in use by your partners or others in their sector, summary of media about your work or important stories in media (e.g. magazine covers, features in national newspapers: “This work was featured in the New York Times (URL)”), awards won by publications related to this topic or by trainees working on this topic, and scholarly responses to your work (e.g. conference panels discussing one of your papers, quotations from book reviews). Provide the context that reviewers need to understand what counts in your field or approach, even if it doesn't show up in citation indexes. See the measures and metrics document for different ways to show a range of impacts.

Remember that the bar is to meet criteria, not exceed on all counts. You can articulate that you meet publication criteria but exceed on impact criteria.

Q: How can I deal with vague or misaligned tenure guidelines?

A: Ask colleagues who recently went through the process to share their materials and advice. Even if guidelines are vague, draft your narrative to explicitly map your contributions to the criteria, defining how you are interpreting and exemplifying general terms. If it redefines categories, say that too, and directly cite institutional values or strategic plans that support your framing. If keywords in the criteria such as “impact,” “excellence,” or “quality” are not defined, it is up to you to define them.

Put another way, you don't make your own criteria (always use your institution's terms!), but you can define the criteria. In some cases, you can also “meet and exceed” problematic terms such as “outreach” by explaining that you do engagement or co-production rather than outreach and noting the differing bars for excellence.

If you have multiple guidelines at the institutional, unit, and department units, locate the documents that identify which take precedence or how they fit together. Be sure to cite which documents you're drawing from in your narrative (e.g. "As per Clause 11.14 in the Collective Agreement....")

Q: Can I include unsuccessful grants in my file?

A: Many institutions now allow this, especially if applications were peer-reviewed, though check with your department head and others who have chaired the P&T committee to identify your institutional culture around documenting effort. Documenting applications that were not accepted can show initiative, competitiveness, and alignment with funding priorities, particularly in first- and third-year reviews. You can also explain strategic withdrawals or changes in project direction. Transparency can reflect well on your judgment and adaptability.

Q: How do I explain stepping away from a project or grant partway through?

A: Include the years in which you were involved, your role, and a short note on why you stepped away, especially if the decision aligned with values-based research, changed community priorities, or shifts in your workload. Frame the departure as a way to say "yes" to these values, not "no" to the project. This kind of integrity is increasingly recognized as good research practice, not a liability.

Q: How do I handle collective authorship or grassroots-authored materials?

A: These certainly count as non-peer-reviewed publications. You can list collective authorship, where the author is an organization's name rather than individuals' names, under a heading like 'Community Publications' or 'Non-Traditional Outputs.' If the author is a group (e.g., 'Northern Youth Coalition'), use that name and explain the structure in a line under the publication in your CV. In the narrative, explain how consensus authorship reflects your commitments to equity, research ethics, or other professional processes.

Q: Can community members or partners serve as external reviewers?

A: In some institutions, yes. You'll often need to request this in advance. If your MOUs with partners or project agreements mention the value of community input and co-evaluation, include these documents in your request. Consider co-review or joint letters if community members are not tenured faculty. Use language in your narrative to validate the expertise of these reviewers (e.g., Traditional Knowledge Holders, organizational leads).

Q: What types of metrics are useful for community-based research?

A: Use both quantitative and qualitative indicators. These might include: number of community partners, number of co-developed outputs, instances of policy uptake through policy citations, media mentions, tools or frameworks still in use, and feedback from community evaluations. You should also consider including a letter of support from your community partners. Avoid overly relying on journal citations and focus on utility, longevity, and co-produced outcomes instead. Resources:

- <https://deakin.libguides.com/research-metrics/NTRO>
- <https://munfa.ca/wp/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/MUN-MUNFA-CA-2023-Appendix-B.pdf>
- <https://zenodo.org/records/15814016>

Q: What should a letter of support from a community partner look like?

A: Your partner can describe their organization/community, their relationship with you and dates inclusive (including any scoping/relationship building at the start), and the outcomes or impacts of your work together. They may also choose to describe what makes your work excellent in terms of process or outcome. It should be clear as to whether the letter is solicited (you asked them to write it for your file) or unsolicited (it was from a funding or award application, or sent as a thank you)

Q: How do I describe interdisciplinary work that falls outside my department's main focus?

A: Use the narrative to map your responsibilities and contributions back to departmental values, being sure to cite those values if they are not in your P&T criteria. Draw connections between your interdisciplinary work and institutional goals or strategic plans. Clarify what portion of your time was allocated to cross-unit work and how that aligns with your appointment letter or performance evaluations, if applicable. If your outputs don't look like those of your colleagues, help reviewers understand why this interdisciplinary is required of the type of research questions or methods you use.

Q: How do you talk about differences in publications for which are first or lead author versus for those where you aren't?

A: In your publication list, you bold your name in author lists so readers can readily scan to see where you fall in author order. You should draw out your first-authored or senior-authored

pieces in terms of the number of publications and the relative impacts of those publications versus those in which you are not first (higher number of community or student co-authors? Larger teams/number of co-authors? More impact in terms of media uptake or citations?). If you are the anchor or senior author (last), describe this in your narrative, since not all disciplines have this tradition and your outside readers may need the context.

For publications in which you are not first author, describe your role in the project. You can place this directly on your CV as well as in the narrative statement. For useful language, see the [CRedit \(Contributor Roles Taxonomy\) Statement](#) used by Elsevier. Some CVs have excerpts of a paper's CRedit statement included in a line under the publication on the CV. You can also include your % contribution to the paper

Q: What kinds of headings can I include in my CV to highlight community-based research?

A: Under publications: Commissioned Publications, Community Reports, White Papers/Policy Papers, Technical Papers, Writing for Public Audiences, Films, Datasets, Documentaries, Training documents, Protocols, Public Scholarship, Infographics (to help formalize any of these that can be public, consider submitting them to a repository that grants DOIs, like Zenodo or FigTree, which also track downloads, views, and citations)

Under funding: Contracts, Commissions

Under Supervision: Informal Mentorship, Youth Mentorship, Mentorship at X Camp/Org

Under Teaching: Capacity Sharing, Capacity Building, Community Workshops, Intensive Trainings, Workshops, Skill Shares, Research Training, and Professional Development or Continuing Professional Development

Under Presentations: Community Presentations, Public Presentations, Invited Consultations, Community Workshops, Expert Role, Expert Witness, Gatherings Organized, Engagement,

Under service: Expert Review (NGOs), Funding Review, Extra-University Committees, Governance Bodies

New headings in a research section: Partnerships (partnership implies a formal agreement like an MOU or contract; otherwise Collaborations), Research Governance (MOUs, Licenses, and Contracts), Case Studies

Remember: If you are providing training, sitting on a committee, or talking to the public specifically because you have a unique skill or knowledge and you are not interchangeable with any other professor, then it is research, not service. By definition, service is part of collegial governance and can (must) be done by any member of the university community equally.

Q: How do you keep things concise when you have many different projects and directions for work?

A: Retroactively narrating your research under a unified trajectory or plan is one of the main tasks of a cover letter and dossier narrative. If you are a community researcher, it may be process and values, rather than discipline and content, that unifies your work. It may be an evolving theory of change, or a dedication to end users that have different needs. You can then articulate the range of content, disciplines, or foci as responsiveness, interdisciplinarity, methodology, or growth (in other words, expert skills!).

Q: How do you recommend external reviewers for your file?

A. Start making a list of people you meet during conferences or meetings and those who chair or are on panels with you. You can also recommend people who you know teach your work (use [Open Syllabus](#) or word of mouth), and you can see who regularly cites your work (using Google Scholar, Web of Science, OpenAlex, or other bibliometric services). You may also want to be strategic about not collaborating with key senior scholars so they can still be external reviewers without a conflict of interest.

Q: How do I cite things in my dossier?

A: You should refer to other documents in your dossier, including P&T criteria, your CV, and your publications. Citing is an easy way to do this, though you can also bold keywords and note clauses. There are three main reasons to cite: it ties your arguments directly back to criteria and evidence, which strengthens your argument, especially if there is an issue with the decision; it clarifies things for external reviewers; and it links your documents together while saving space. You can use in-text referencing like (Allaba et al 2022) or (MUNFA §2.3). The silcrow sign (§) means “section” and can be used to note CV headings or P&T clauses. You may want to use footnotes, but they should only be for references. Many formats include a references list at the end of a dossier.

Q: How do I track and manage CV items over the long term?

A: Use a 'living CV' document that you update quarterly. Create email filters (e.g., 'Put this on your CV') or calendar reminders to add new presentations, meetings, and outputs. Many researchers keep a plain-text 'CV diary' or spreadsheet to track small items, such as participation in working groups or informal consultations. This reduces stress when preparing for major file updates.

Q: How long should my file be?

A: Some institutions have a word or page count. If yours doesn't, longer isn't better: concise and clear is better than long (think of graduate theses that get overlong). The committee and outside readers are obliged to read anything you put in the file, so be complete but kind to your readers.

Q: What do I do if this FAQ and my university or department disagree on a point?

A: Your institution and its criteria and culture as the single most important guide for promotion and tenure. Make sure you prioritize *documented* P&T criteria and guidelines first, then the culture and norms of your unit: ask multiple people including colleagues, your department head, and former chairs or members of P&T committees. If you are concerned you won't be awarded tenure due to translating your research into institutional norms, the documented P&T criteria will be the sole source of appeals, as they are governing documents. If you have a union and have concerns about not being awarded P&T because of your community work, then speak to them before you prepare your file.